

Comparative Study of Epidural Ropivacaine 0.75% and Bupivacaine 0.5% with Fentanyl for Elective Caesarean Section in Telangana PopulationBariki Santhosh Kumar¹, Pradeep Kode²¹Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, TRR Institute of medical sciences, Inole Patancheru, Sangareddy (Dist), Telangana, India, 502319²Associate Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Bhaskara Medical College, Yenkapally (V), Moinabad (M), K.V. Rangareddy (D), Telanagana, India, 500075

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Abstract:**Background:** Both Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine are relatively new long acting amide local anesthetics. Both are pure s-enantiomers of the parent drug racemic Bupivacaine. Little is known as the efficacy of epidural action of Bupivacaine with Fentanyl when compared with Ropivacaine.**Method:** Out of 90 patients, 45 received 10 mg hyperbaric Bupivacaine with 20 micrograms of Fentanyl, and 45 (group RF) received 15 mg hyperbaric Ropivacaine with 20 micrograms of Fentanyl. We compared the APGAR scores for hemodynamic parameters, sensory, and motor blockage in both groups.**Results:** Demographic profile, i.e., weight, height, BMI The duration of surgery was the same in both groups (p > 0.001 was insignificant), and motor and sensory blockades were highly significant (p<0.001). VAS scores at 4 hours, 6 hours, and 8 hours had a significant p value (p<0.001). Agar score at 1 minute was also highly significant (p<0.005).**Conclusion:** In the present study, it was proved that hyperbaric Ropivacaine with Fentanyl is a better alternative to hyperbaric Bupivacaine with Fentanyl in LSCS patients of c-section.**Keywords:** Bupivacaine, Fentanyl, Ropivacaine, VAS Analogue, Hemodynamic.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Caesarean sections are being increasingly done for maternal as well as fetal indication. The maternal indications are cephalopelvic chorio-amnionitis, chloriamnionitis, non-progression or obstructed labor, and previous caesarean sections.

The usual fetal indications include a large for gestational age fetus, an unfavorable lie, and fetal distress due to any cause. Lower segment caesarean section (LSCS) is routinely done under spinal anesthesia except in cases where either spinal anesthesia is contraindicated, such as patient refusal injection site infections. (Severe thrombocytopenia and uncorrected hypovolemia), regional anesthesia is widely considered the technique of choice for caesarean sections, and although de nova epidural anesthesia is currently much less popular than spinal anesthesia, it is still an important technique [1].

Ropivacaine 0.5% has been found to be an effective agent for providing epidural anesthesia for caesarean sections, providing similar satisfactory conditions to 0.5% of Bupivacaine. Among all solutions for providing de nova epidural anesthesia, which included a mixture of Ropivacaine 0.75 with

Fentanyl and/or Bupivacaine 0.5% with Fentanyl, the most popular techniques in elective caesarean sections.

However, any mixture of Bupivacaine and Fentanyl is unlicensed, and since it is not commercially available, it needs to be made up on an individual basis. It is reported that using 0.75% Ropivacaine with Fentanyl was also very effective. Bupivacaine, Ropivacaine, and Mepivacaine are common drugs used for spinal anesthesia. In the present study, Ropivacaine 0.75% and Bupivacaine 0.5% with Fentanyl were compared for elective caesarean sections.

Total motor and sensory blockade, hemodynamic, parameters VAS scores were used, and effects of both groups were studied. Maternal and fetal side effects were also noted.

Material and Methods

90 (ninty) patients admitted to the obstetrics and gynaecology department of the TRR Institute of Medical Sciences, Inole Patancheru, Sangareddy (dist), Telangana were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: ASAI and ASS-II, aged 20 to 45 years, patients willing to undergo elective LSCS were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients ASA III not willing to undergo LSCS surgery, women who had undergone previous surgery, scoliosis, or injury to back patients who have an allergy to amide local anesthetics. Women's history of stillborn babies was excluded from the study.

Method: Every patient was premedicated with oral Ranitidine 150 mg and Metaclopramide 10 mg. On arrival in the theater suite, they were given 25 ml of 0.3 M Sodium citrate orally. Out of 90, 40 patients were classified into two groups.

Group BF: Received 10 mg hyperbaric Bupivacaine with 20 micrograms of Fentanyl.

Group RF: Received 15 mg hyperbaric Ropivacaine with 20 micrograms Fentanyl.

Basic investigations such as CBC, coagulation profile, HbsAg, and HIV were done in all cases, if not already done. After shifting to the operation theater, venous access was secured with 20 G intracanth, and 500 mL Ringer lactate was started. ECG monitoring of SPO₂ and non-invasive blood pressure monitoring was started. Spinal anesthesia was given using standard practice. All patients received 500 ml of Ringer lactate and the first dosage of third-generation cephalosporin before giving spinal anesthesia. Patients either received Bupivacaine and Fentanyl or Ropivacaine and Fentanyl depending upon the group to which they belonged. The onset and duration of analgesics were noted. Hemodynamic parameters such as HR (heart rate), systolic as well as diastolic pressure, respiratory rate, and SPO₂ were monitored. APGAR score at 1 minute and 5 minutes was analyzed to know immediate neonatal outcomes. VAS (visual analogue scale) was determined every 5 minutes rather than every 30 minutes up to 5 hours to assess the severity of postoperative pain. The incidence of complications such as hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, and shivering was noted.

Duration of study was from May 2023 to June 2024.

Statistical Analysis: Demographic profiles of motor and sensory blockade VPS score and APGAR score were compared in both groups with z test. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Comparison of demographics profile in both groups-

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic profile in both groups (Total No. of patients: 90)

Particulars	Group-B Mean value \pm SD 45	Group-R Mean value \pm SD 45	t test	p value
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Weight: 61.29 (\pm 5.18) in group B, 59.20 (\pm 6.26) in group R, t test was 1.72 and $p > 0.95$ (p value is Insignificant)

Height (cm): 152.58 (\pm 5.23) in group B, 154.20 (\pm 4.98) in group R, t test was 1.57 and $p > 0.04$ (p value is Insignificant).

BMI: 24.08 (\pm 1.50) in group B, 24.29 (\pm 1.59) in group R, t test was 0.64 and $p > 0.52$ (p value is Insignificant).

Duration of surgery: 58.09 (\pm 6.12) in group-B, 56.20 (\pm 4.88) in group R, t test was 1.9 and $p > 0.55$ (p value is Insignificant).

Table 2: Comparison of motor and sensory blockades in both groups

- Onset of sensory Blockades: 152.5 (\pm 15.29) in group B, 186.38 (\pm 20.15) in group R, t test was 8.98 and $p < 0.001$.
- Onset of motor Block (seconds) – 322.5 (\pm 28.12) in group B, 360.54 (\pm 36.20) in group R, t test was 5.56 and $p < 0.001$.
- Mean time to achieve highest level of sensory analgesia (seconds): 133.28 (\pm 24.50) in group B, 382.65 (\pm 26.82) in group R, t test was 9.11 and $p < 0.001$.
- Mean time to sensory regression (minutes): 132.50 (\pm 10.14) in group B, 98.11 (\pm 9.28) in group R, t test was 16.7 and $p < 0.001$.
- Duration of motor Block (Minutes): 182.00 (\pm 20.58) in group B, 123.5 (\pm 14.38) in group R, t test was 9.08 and $p < 0.001$
- Duration of analgesia: 275.86 (\pm 40.33) in group B, 184.65 (\pm 30.11) in group R, t test was 12.15 and $p < 0.001$.

Table 3: Comparison of VAS score in both groups

- 180 Minutes: 1.18 (\pm 0.40) in group B, 1.36 (\pm 0.52) in group R, t test was 1.86 and $p < 0.001$
- 4 hours: 2.12 (\pm 0.60) in group B, 2.92 (\pm 0.68) in group R, t test was 5.91 and $p < 0.001$
- 6 hours: 4.12 (\pm 0.40) in group B, 4.60 (\pm 0.42) in group R, t test was 5.55 and $p < 0.001$.
- 8 hours: 5.12 (\pm 1.12) in group B, 5.30 (\pm 1.32) in group-R, t test was 0.89 and $p > 0.68$ (p value is Insignificant).

Table 4: Comparison of APGAR score in both groups

APGAR at 1 minute: 8.6 (\pm 0.45) in group B, 9.06 (\pm 0.49) in group R, t test was 4.63 and $p < 0.005$

APGAR at 5 minute: 9.29 (\pm 0.38) in group-B, 9.30 (\pm 0.54) in group R, t test was 0.10 and $p > 0.98$ (p value is Insignificant).

Weight (Kg)	61.29 (± 5.18)	59.20 (± 6.26)	1.70	p>0.95
Height (cm)	152.58 (± 5.23)	154.20 (± 4.498)	1.57	p>0.04
BMI	24.08 (± 1.50)	24.29 (± 1.58)	0.64	p>0.52
Duration of surgery (minutes)	58.08 (± 6.12)	56.20(± 1.8)	1.9	p>0.55

(P value is insignificant in all parameter)

Figure 1: Comparison of Demographic profile in both groups

Table 2: Comparison of Motor and sensory blockades in both groups

Parameters	Group-B Mean value ± SD (45)	Group-R Mean value ± SD (45)	t test	p value
Onset of sensory blockades	152.5 (± 15.29)	186.38 (± 20.15)	8.98	P<0.001
Onset motor Block (seconds)	322.5 (± 28.12)	360.54 (± 36.20)	5.56	P<0.0001
Mean time to achieve highest level of sensory Analgesia (sec)	333.28 (± 24.50)	382.65 (± 26.82)	9.11	P<0.001
Mean time to sensory regressive (Minutes)	132.50 (± 10.14)	98.11 (± 9.28)	16.7	P<0.001
Duration of motor Block (Minutes)	180.00 (± 20.58)	122.5 (± 14.38)	9.08	P<0.001
Duration of Analgesia (Minutes)	276.86 (± 40.33)	182.65 (± 30.11)	12.15	P<0.001

(P value is highly insignificant in all parameters)

Figure 2: Comparison of Motor and sensory blockades in both groups

Table 3: Comparison of Mean VAS scores in both groups

Time	Group-B (45)	Group-R (45)	t test	p value
Immediate post-operative period	00	00	--	--
30 Minutes	00	00	--	--
60 Minutes	00	00		
90 Minutes	00	00		
120 Minutes	00	00		
150 Minutes	00	00		
180 Minutes	1.18 (± 0.40)	1.36 (± 0.53)	1.84	P<0.18
4 Hours	2.12 (± 0.60)	2.92 (± 0.68)	5.91	P<0.001
6 hours	4.12 (± 0.40)	4.60 (± 0.42)	5.55	P<0.001
8 hours	5.12 (± 1.12)	5.30 (± 1.32)	0.69	p>0.89

Figure 3: Comparison of Mean VAS scores in both groups

Table 4: Comparison of Mean APGAR scores in both groups

APGAR	Group-B (45)	Group-R (45)	t test	p value
APGAR at 1 minutes	8.6 (± 0.45)	9.06 (± 0.49)	4.63	P<0.005
APGAR at 5 minutes	9.29 (± 0.38)	9.30 (± 0.54)	0.10	P>0.98

Figure 4: Comparison of Mean APGAR scores in both groups

Discussion

In the present comparative study of epidural Ropivacaine 0.75% and Bupivacaine 0.5% with Fentanyl for elective caesarean sections in the Telangana population. In the comparison of demographic profile in both groups, weight, height, BMI, and duration of surgery had an insignificant p value (Table 1). In the comparison of motor and sensory blockages in both groups, onset of sensory block and onset of motor block mean time to achieve the highest level of sensory analgesia (seconds mean time to sensory regress). Duration of motor block and duration of analgesia had highly significant p values ($p < 0.001$) (Table-2). In the comparison of VAS score in both groups, 180 minutes, 4 hours, and 6 hours had a significant p value ($p < 0.001$) but at 8 hours, the p value had an insignificant p value ($p > 0.89$) (Table-3). Comparison of Mean APGAR scores in both groups at 1 minute 8.6 (0.49) in group R, t test was 4.63 and $p < 0.005$, APGAR at 5 minutes 9.29 (± 0.38) in group B, 9.30 (± 0.54) + in group R, t test was 0.10 and $p > 0.98$ (p value is insignificant) (Table 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Though Bupivacaine has been the very popular anesthetic agent for various surgeries, for its long-acting local anesthetic profile. Its use, however, is associated with side effects including central nervous system and neurotoxicity [8]. Ropivacaine is better in comparison to Bupivacaine because of its fewest side effects, like retention of urine, brady-

cardia, and hypotension. Moreover, ropivacaine is less lipophilic as compared to bupivacaine; hence, it does not penetrate large myelins, causing a reduced motor blockade and least neurotoxicity, but Ropivacaine is an equally effective analgesic as Bupivacaine [9]. Hence, Ropivacaine is being preferred over Bupivacaine for various surgeries.

Ropivacaine is a potentially superior agent to Bupivacaine because of its lower toxicity and less motor block. Experiments in lower animals have also reported that ropivacaine is less cardiotoxic than bupivacaine. Ropivacaine produces more fewer arrhythmias than Bupivacaine in the isolated perfused rabbit heart [10]. The same study of comparison of Ropivacaine and Fentanyl with Bupivacaine plus Fentanyl was conducted by many authors and noted that there were no significant changes in hemodynamic parameters VAS scores except low diastolic pressure at 360 minutes in group R (the Ropivacaine group), and no adverse effects like nausea, vomiting, and hypotension were observed in the R group [11].

In the present study, it was observed that sensory block was shorter in the Ropivacaine group than the Bupivacaine group. Moreover, Ropivacaine also produced a shorter duration of motor blockage than Bupivacaine, but hemodynamic parameters such as systolic and diastolic blood pressure have no significant difference, but the HR of patients in the Bupivacaine group was higher than the Ropivacaine group. Hence, Ropivacaine is a better choice

due to its little influence on hemodynamics and shorter duration of sensory block and motor block, which are useful for the recovery and also safe for the patients [12]. Bupivacaine being neurotoxic, its group patients have more nausea/vomiting bradycardia, and hypotension, which is observed, which causes panic in patients and worries for anesthesiologists.

Summary and Conclusion

Present comparative study of epidural Ropivacaine 0.75% and Bupivacaine with Fentanyl for elective caesarean section in Telangana population. It was observed that ropivacaine is a better alternative to Bupivacaine because of its least neurotoxic and cardiotoxic side effects. Moreover, Ropivacaine has a shorter duration of sensory and motor blockage. The present study demands such clinical trials in a large number of patients to confirm the significant findings of the present study.

Limitation of Study: Owing to the tertiary location of the research center, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest technologies, we have limited findings and results.

This research work was approved by the ethical committee of the TRR Institute of Medical Sciences, Inole Patancheru, Sangareddy (dist), Telangana.

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